

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge in the Extended Covid-19 Pandemic

Roberto Suson 1a: Cebu Technological University College of Education & Technology – Education and Technology, Cebu City, Cebu 6000, Philippines <http://orcid.org/0000-0003-0194-572X>

Corresponding Author: robertosuson29@gmail.com

Abstract. As the world becomes more digital and the Covid-19 epidemic emerges, it has an influence on the lives of educators and other stakeholders. This research sheds light on educators' pedagogical, material, and technical fluency when it comes to using technology in the classroom. The results revealed that educators understood the potential of technology in the classroom, how it might be used to teach a variety of subjects, and what constitutes good practices for integrating technology into the curriculum. The data also suggested that educators had some familiarity with tech-based instruction. However, the data shows that some people had difficulties with the technical aspects of integrating technology.

Keywords: TPACK, Technology integration, technical Issues,

1. Introduction

Globally, students' use of technology both inside and outside of the classroom has grown substantially especially in times of pandemic. Despite these benefits, many teachers remain resistant to integrating technology into their classrooms (Berge and Collins, 1995; Hwang et al, 2015; Lau, 2003; Maor, 2003). A lack of knowledge about how technology may best be utilized to educate students in particular subjects is also a major barrier in the classroom, in addition to the usual issues of cost, accessibility, and implementation time (Kurt, 2019). New possibilities for gathering and analyzing information exist in all fields of study thanks to the proliferation of ICT in the twenty-first century. In addition, ICT is reshaping the classroom by introducing novel approaches to student participation (TTF, 2018; Noor-Ul-Amin, 2013; Benton-Borgh, 2013).

As new forms of digital technology become more widely available and find meaningful social uses in everyday life, they can more readily be incorporated into existing educational programs (Merchant, 2012; Sefton-green, 2004). Teachers confront a number of questions and concerns regarding how and when to use emerging technologies to enhance instruction and student learning. As a result, the qualities, affordances, and constraints of individual technologies have taken a backseat to students' thinking, curricular material, and pedagogical practices in the context of learning with new technology (Niess, 2011).

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Teachers should consider how their content knowledge interacts with TPACK (Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge) to better incorporate technology into their lessons and increase student engagement. In the context of the TPACK framework, content (CK), pedagogical content (PK), and technological content (T) all play significant roles (TK). The TPACK framework considers all three strands of knowledge together. The TPACK paradigm goes further by placing an emphasis on the intersection of three distinct types of knowledge: pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), technological content knowledge (TCK), and technological pedagogical know-how (TPACK). For efficient technology integration in pedagogy centered on particular subject matter, it is necessary to develop attention to the dynamic, transactional interaction between different components of knowledge situated in specific settings. Because of the variety of contexts in which education takes place, there is no universal formula for combining content, technology, and pedagogy that will work for every instructor, subject area, or method. Aspects such as individual educators, courses, grade levels, school-specific demographics, culture, and more (Mkoehler, 2012).

Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge. One of the first works on the TPACK paradigm was "Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge: A Framework for Teacher Knowledge" by Punya Mishra and Matthew J. Koehler, published in 2006. They say that they came at this conclusion after five years of study in which they conducted design experiments to monitor how teachers at different grade levels conducted their lessons (Wang, 2019). Their motivation came from Lee S. Shulman's "Those Who Understand: Knowledge Growth in Teaching" from 1986. One typical view of teachers' expertise is that they need to possess both subject matter expertise and pedagogical understanding. Shulman argues otherwise, saying that excellent teachers use the two bodies of knowledge to better understand their subject matter and how to convey it to students. He calls this kind of information "pedagogical content knowledge" (PCK). Twenty years later, Mishra and Koehler observed that the most noticeable change in education was the introduction of technological tools into the classroom. Unlike PCK, technical knowledge was found to be treated as if it were in its own category. Over the course of five years, these researchers developed a new framework called TPACK, which integrates technology into subject knowledge instruction while placing special emphasis on the interconnections among and limitations on each of the three types of knowledge that teachers must consider in their classrooms (Mouza et al., 2014).

Content Knowledge (CK). It includes not only the ideas, theories, facts, and organizational structures unique to a certain academic discipline, but also the tried-and-true methods for conveying this information to pupils. Middle school history and science classes, for instance, don't have to cover as much ground as their undergraduate or graduate school counterparts, hence the amount of CK imparted by teachers or the material covered in each lesson may differ. Ball et al. (2008); Harris et al. (2009); Mkwawa (2020).

Pedagogical Knowledge (PK). What is described here is the knowledge of educators on methods, processes, and strategies for educating and training students. Specific domains where PK is put to use include pedagogical competencies including identifying student learning styles, managing classroom behavior, planning lessons, and evaluating student progress. Harris et al. (2009); Mishra and koeler (2008); Graham (2011).

Technological Knowledge (TK). This pertains to the extent to which educators are familiar with and adept at using a variety of technological tools and resources. TK entails not just keeping up with and making use of new technologies as they become

available, but also developing the ability to recognize when educational technologies aid or impede student learning. The literature on this topic is extensive (Mouza et al., 2014; Koeler & Mishra, 2009; Niess et al., 2009). A new paradigm has emerged for envisioning teacher expertise, despite the fact that teacher preparation programs have failed to actively involve instructors in the incorporation of appropriate technologies. Shulman (1987) recognized the need for a broader perspective when he established PCK, and since then many academics have advised thinking about the integration of technology, content, and pedagogy in the same way. Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPCK) is an effort to bridge the gap between the traditionally separate disciplines of content, pedagogy (the study of teaching and learning), and technology (Margerum-Leys & Marx, 2002; Mishra & Koehler, 2006). Originally an acronym for "technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge," TPACK (pronounced "tee-pack") was later coined to emphasize the integration of all three into the classroom (Niess, 2008b; Thompson & Mishra, 2007). TPACK is considered as a dynamic framework that defines the information that teachers need to depend on when employing digital technology to support students' thinking and learning across a wide range of subjects.

From these images and perspectives, we were able to extract the core features of TPACK. TPACK develops and teachers' knowledge is represented in more dynamic (rather than static) ways when they incorporate new technologies into their instruction of certain subject areas. Angeli and Valanides provided two major findings (2009). The term "technology" was deemed misleading; thus the term was changed to "Information and Communication Technologies" (ICTs) (ICT). It was also described as "a tool utilized by its users to reconstruct subject matter from teacher knowledge into the content of instruction" (pp. 8-9). According to their findings, "simply establishing one or more of its knowledge bases does not ensure or suggest that ICT-TPCK is also being produced concurrently" (p. 14). With the addition of the technology domain's intersection with the PCK content and pedagogy junction, the name "technology pedagogical content knowledge" was chosen to emphasize TPACK as a PCK extension (Niess, 2005). In place of the word "pedagogy," this phrase emphasized the breadth and depth of the many contributing variables to effective education (Niess, 2005). There is a broad variety of approaches that focus on the classroom in which teachers are expected to incorporate technology advances (Angeli & Valanides, 2009; Doering et al., 2009; Koehler & Mishra, 2008). Teachers' ability to think across several construct domains at once was highlighted in the encounter narratives. Niess (2008a) defines TPACK strategic thinking as knowing when, why, and how to use domain-specific knowledge and procedures (Shavelson, Ruiz-Primo, Li, & Ayala, 2003) in guiding student learning using appropriate information and communication technologies (as cited by Niess, 2011).

2. Purpose of the Study

This research assessed the faculties level of Technological pedagogical content knowledge in the extended covid-19 pandemic.

3. Research Methodology

A descriptive method research design based on quantitative methods was employed for this investigation. Reports that summarize key facts are the product of descriptive statistics, which use data collection and analytic methods to do so. The study's findings give information on important aspects of technology Content by the faculty. The tool, a 5-point Likert-scale survey, was adapted from research conducted by Schmidt et al. (2009) and Valtonen et al. (2017) on teachers' TPACK. All of the tools, methods, materials, and information necessary are included here. In light of the current epidemic, this research focused on educators' pedagogical, content, and technical competence.

4. Results and Discussions

Table 1. Pedagogical Knowledge

Pedagogical Knowledge	Mean	VD
Guiding students' discussions during group work	4.42	SK
Promoting critical thinking in students	4.68	SK
Assisting students in the planning of their own learning	4.84	SK
Assisting pupils with their reflective thinking	4.65	SK
Encouraging pupils to utilize one other's opinions and ideas throughout group projects.	4.62	SK
Aiding kids' problem-solving abilities	4.54	SK
Fostering pupils' inventiveness	4.52	SK
Weighted mean	4.61	SK

Table 1, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of pedagogical knowledge. Guiding students in planning their own learning got the highest weighted Guiding students' discussions during group work got the lowest weighted mean of 4.42 which also verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of pedagogical knowledge got an overall mean score of 4.61 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. Persaud (2019) has stated that having a well-thought-out pedagogy can improve the quality of your teaching and the way students learn, helping them gain a deeper grasp of fundamental material. Being mindful of the way you teach can help you better understand how help students achieve deeper learning. And it can, in turn, impact student perception, resulting in cooperative learning environments that utilizes technology. This indicates that pedagogical knowledge integrating technology is fundamental in 21st century classroom. Moreover, pedagogy requires meaningful classroom interactions and respect between educators and learners. The goal is to help students build on prior learning and develop skills and attitudes and for educators to devise and present curriculum in a way that is relevant to students, aligning with their needs and cultures.

Table 2. Technological knowledge (TK)

Technological knowledge (TK)	Mean	VD
I am capable at resolving ICT-related issues.	4.16	K
I am well-versed in new technologies and their features.	4.12	K
I am capable at utilizing modern technology.	4.11	K
I am familiar with a number of new technology websites.	4.08	K
I know how to troubleshoot ICT problem	3.48	K
It's easy for me to incorporate technological aspects in my class	3.88	K
I can solve ICT related problems	4.12	K
Weighted mean	3.99	K

Table 2, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of technological knowledge. the statement "I can solve ICT related problems" got the highest weighted mean of 4.16 which verbally described as knowledgeable. While, the statement "I know how to troubleshoot ICT problem" got the lowest weighted mean of 3.88 which also verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of technological knowledge got an overall mean score of 3.99 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Recent reports shows that technical skills are important for a number of reasons. They can help you work more efficiently, boost your confidence and make you a more valuable candidate for employers. Candidates who have a technical skill are often more confident when applying to certain industries than those who don't (WikiJob, 2020). Hence, this indicates that technological knowledge of the teachers is important to help students in this digital world.

Table 3. Content knowledge (CK)

Content knowledge (CK)	Mean	VD
I have sufficient knowledge in developing contents in my lessons	4.84	SK
I know the basic theories and concepts of my lessons	4.83	SK
I know the history and development of important theories in my lessons	4.86	SK
I am familiar with recent research in my lessons	4.55	SK
Weighted mean	4.77	SK

Table 3, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of content knowledge. the statement "I know the history and development of important theories in my lessons" got the highest weighted mean of 4.86 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. While, the statement "I am familiar with recent research in my lessons" got the lowest weighted mean of 4.55 which also verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of content knowledge got an overall mean score of 4.77 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Our own content knowledge affects how we interpret the content goals we are expected to reach with our students. It affects the way we hear and respond to our students and their questions. It affects our ability to explain clearly and to ask good questions. It affects our ability to approach a mathematical idea flexibly with our students and to make connections. It affects our ability to push each student at that special moment when he or she is ready or curious. And it affects our ability to make those moments happen more often for our students (Lappan, 2000). Moreover, teacher content knowledge is crucially important to the improvement of teaching and learning, attention to its development (Ball et al., 2008).

Table 4. Interaction between technological and pedagogical knowledge (TPK)

Interaction between technological and pedagogical knowledge	Mean	VD
I understand how to utilize ICT in the classroom as a tool for students' reflective thinking.	3.82	K
I understand how to utilize ICT in the classroom as a tool for students to design their own learning.	3.34	K
I understand how to utilize ICT in the classroom as a tool for exchanging ideas and thinking together.	4.06	K
I also understand how to use ICT in the classroom as a tool for students' creative thinking.	4.16	K

I understand how to use ICT in the classroom as a tool for group problem solving among students.	3.84	K
Weighted mean	3.84	K

Table 4, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of Interaction between technological and pedagogical knowledge. The statement "I know how to use ICT in teaching as a tool for students' creative thinking" got the highest weighted mean of 4.16 which verbally described as knowledgeable. While, the statement " I know how to use ICT in teaching as a tool for students to plan their own learning" got the lowest weighted mean of 3.34 which also verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of interaction between technological and pedagogical knowledge got an overall mean score of 3.84 which verbally described as knowledgeable. This describes teachers' understanding of how technology and content can both influence and push against each other. Kurt (2019) has stated that TCK involves understanding how the subject matter can be communicated via different edtech offerings, and considering which specific edtech tools might be best suited for specific subject matters or classrooms.

Table 5. Interaction between content and technological knowledge

Interaction between content and technological knowledge (TCK)	Mean	VD
I know websites with online materials for my study.	4.63	SK
Professionals utilize ICT apps that I am familiar with.	4.48	SK
I am familiar with ICT-applications that I may utilize to better grasp the topics.	4.12	K
I am familiar with technology that can be used to demonstrate challenging concepts.	4.25	SK
Weighted mean	4.37	SK

Table 5, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of interaction between content and technological knowledge. The statement "I know websites with online materials for my study" got the highest weighted mean of 4.63 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. While, the statement "I know ICT-applications which I can use to better understand the contents" got the lowest weighted mean of 4.12 which also verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of interaction between content and technological knowledge got an overall mean score of 4.37 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. Thus, understanding of how technology and content can both influence and push against each other.

Table 6. Interaction between pedagogical and content knowledge (PCK)

Interaction between pedagogical and content knowledge (PCK)	Mean	VD
I know how to help students solve content-related problems in groups.	4.84	SK
I understand how to direct pupils' critical thinking.	4.64	SK
I know how to encourage students to use one other's opinions and ideas in group projects.	4.88	SK
I also know how to encourage students' reflective thinking.	4.82	SK
I know how to assist pupils in developing their own learning plans.	4.85	SK
Weighted mean	4.81	SK

Table 6, shows the teachers knowledge in terms of interaction between pedagogical and content knowledge. The statement "I know how to guide students in planning their own learning" got the highest weighted mean of 4.88 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. While, the statement "I know how to guide students' critical thinking" got the lowest weighted mean of 4.64 which also verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of interaction between pedagogical and content knowledge got an overall mean score of 4.81 which verbally described as strongly knowledgeable. According to Solis (2009) pedagogical content knowledge is a special combination of content and pedagogy that is uniquely constructed by teachers and thus is the "special" form of an educator's professional knowing and understanding.

Table 7. Interaction between pedagogical, technological, and content knowledge (TPACK)

Interaction between pedagogical, technological, and content knowledge	Mean	VD
I know how to utilize ICT as a tool for exchanging ideas and collaborative thinking when teaching natural sciences.	3.81	K
I know how to utilize ICT as a tool for students' reflective thinking when teaching natural sciences.	3.64	K
I know how to utilize ICT as a tool for students to design their own learning when teaching natural sciences.	4.12	K
I know how to use ICT as a tool for group problem solving in natural sciences classes.	4.06	K
I know how to use ICT as a tool for students' creative thinking when teaching natural sciences.	3.86	K
Weighted mean	3.90	K

Table 7, shows the teachers knowledge in interaction between pedagogical, technological, and content knowledge. The statement " In teaching natural sciences, I know how to use ICT as a tool for students to plan their own learning" got the highest weighted mean of 4.12 which verbally described as knowledgeable. While, the statement "In teaching natural sciences, I know how to use ICT as a tool for sharing ideas and thinking together" got the lowest weighted mean of 3.64 which also verbally described as knowledgeable. Overall, the knowledge of interaction between pedagogical, technological, and content knowledge got an overall mean score of 3.90 which verbally described as knowledgeable. Teaching with technology is complicated further considering the challenges newer technologies present to teachers. Technological pedagogical content knowledge is an understanding that emerges from interactions among content, pedagogy, and technology knowledge. Underlying truly meaningful and deeply skilled teaching with technology, TPACK is different from knowledge of all three concepts individually. Teaching with technology is a difficult thing to do well. The TPACK framework suggests that content, pedagogy, technology, and teaching/learning contexts have roles to play individually and together. Teaching successfully with technology requires continually creating, maintaining, and re-establishing a dynamic equilibrium among all components. It is worth noting that a range of factors influences how this equilibrium is reached (Harris et al. 2009)

4. CONCLUSION

Research shows that faculty have acquired the skills necessary to integrate technology into their lessons. This shows that educators were given comprehensive guidance on how to optimally use technology into their classrooms and online curricula. Major results also imply that instructors and students were able to accomplish department of education goals under the new normal because of the inclusion of technology. But the data also hints to some hiccups with the use of technology in the classroom. Recognizing the significance of these findings highlights the need of offering supplementary educational options in order to maintain high standards of education.

RECOMMENDATION

The main goal of this study is to gain empirical knowledge on the faculty's knowledge in terms technology, content, and technological knowledge as means of instruction and learning.

References

- Angeli, C. M., & Valanides, N. (2009, April). Examining epistemological and methodological issues of the conceptualizations, development and assessment of ICT-TPACK: Advancing Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPCK)—Part I. Teachers. Paper presented at the meeting of the American Educational Research Association (AERA) Annual Conference, San Diego, CA.
- Ball, D. L., Thames, M. H., & Phelps, G. (2008). Content knowledge for teaching: What makes it special. *Journal of teacher education*, 59(5), 389-407.
- Berge, Z. L., & Collins, M. P. (Eds.). (1995). *Computer mediated communication and the online classroom: distance learning*. Cresskill: Hampton press.
- Benton-Borghini, B. H. (2013). A Universally Designed for Learning (UDL) infused Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) practitioners' model essential for teacher preparation in the 21st Century. *Journal of educational computing research*, 48(2), 245-265.
- Doering, A., Veletsianos, G., & Scharber, C. (2009, April). Using the technological, pedagogical and content knowledge framework in professional development. Paper presented at the annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association (AERA), San Diego, CA.
- Harris, J., Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. (2009). Teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge and learning activity types: Curriculum-based technology integration reframed. *Journal of research on technology in education*, 41(4), 393-416.
- Hwang, G. J., Lai, C. L., & Wang, S. Y. (2015). Seamless flipped learning: a mobile technology-enhanced flipped classroom with effective learning strategies. *Journal of computers in education*, 2(4), 449-473.

- Graham, C. R. (2011). Theoretical considerations for understanding technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). *Computers & Education*, 57(3), 1953-1960.
- Kurt, S. (2018). TPACK: Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Framework. Retrieved from: <https://educationaltechnology.net/technological-pedagogical-content-knowledge-tpack-framework/>
- Kurt, S. (2019). TPACK: Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Framework. Educational Technology. Retrieved from <https://educationaltechnology.net/technological-pedagogical-content-knowledgetpack-framework/>
- Kurt, S. "TPACK: Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge Framework," in *Educational Technology*, May 12, 2018. Retrieved from <https://educationaltechnology.net/technological-pedagogical-content-knowledge-tpack-framework/>
- Lappan, G. (2000). A vision of learning to teach for the 21st century. *School science and mathematics*, 100(6), 319-326.
- Lau, L. K. (2003). Institutional factors affecting student retention. *Education*, 124(1).
- Merchant, G. (2012). Mobile practices in everyday life: Popular digital technologies and schooling revisited. *British Journal of Educational Technology*, 43(5), 770-782.
- Mkoehler. (2012). Seven components of TPACK. Retrieved from: <https://matt-koehler.com/tpack2/tpack-explained/>
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2006). Technological pedagogical content knowledge: A framework for integrating technology in teachers' knowledge. *Teachers College Record*, 108 (6), 1017–1054
- Margerum-Leys, J., & Marx, R. W. (2002). The nature and sharing of teacher knowledge of technology in a student teachers/mentor teacher pair. *Journal of Teacher Education*, 55(5), 421-437.
- Maor, D. (2003). The teacher's role in developing interaction and reflection in an online learning community. *Educational Media International*, 40(1-2), 127-138.
- Mouza, C., Karchmer-Klein, R., Nandakumar, R., Ozden, S. Y., & Hu, L. (2014). Investigating the impact of an integrated approach to the development of preservice teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). *Computers & Education*, 71, 206-221.
- Mkwawa, D. (2020). Creating Digitally Ready Secondary Schools' Students in Tanzania.
- Mishra, P., & Koehler, M. J. (2008, March). Introducing technological pedagogical content knowledge. In annual meeting of the American Educational Research Association (pp. 1-16).
- Mouza, C., Karchmer-Klein, R., Nandakumar, R., Ozden, S. Y., & Hu, L. (2014). Investigating the impact of an integrated approach to the development of preservice teachers' technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK). *Computers & Education*, 71, 206-221.

- Niess, M. L., Ronau, R. N., Shafer, K. G., Driskell, S. O., Harper, S. R., Johnston, C., ... & Kersaint, G. (2009). Mathematics teacher TPACK standards and development model. *Contemporary issues in technology and teacher education*, 9(1), 4-24.
- Noor-Ul-Amin, S. (2013). An effective use of ICT for education and learning by drawing on worldwide knowledge, research, and experience. *ICT as a Change Agent for Education*. India: Department of Education, University of Kashmir, 1-13.
- Niess, M. L. (2005). Preparing teachers to teach science and mathematics with technology: Developing a technology pedagogical content knowledge. *Teaching and Teacher Education*, 21(5), 509-523
- Niess, M. L. (2011). Investigating TPACK: Knowledge growth in teaching with technology. *Journal of educational computing research*, 44(3), 299-317.
- Teaching Teachers for the Future. (2018). What is TPACK. Retrieved from: <https://www.ttf.edu.au/what-is-tpack/what-is-tpack.html>
- Shavelson, R., Ruiz-Primo, A., Li, M., & Ayala, C. (2003). Evaluating new approaches to assessing learning (CSE Report 604). Los Angeles, CA: University of California, National Center for Research on Evaluation.
- Schmidt, D. A., Baran, E., Thompson, A. D., Mishra, P., Koehler, M. J., & Shin, T. S. (2009). Technological pedagogical content knowledge (TPACK) the development and validation of an assessment instrument for preservice teachers. *Journal of research on Technology in Education*, 42(2), 123-149.
- Shulman, L. (1987). Knowledge and teaching: Foundations of the new reform. *Harvard Educational Review*, 57(1), 1-22.
- Thompson, A. D., & Mishra, P. (2007). Breaking news: TPCK becomes TPACK! *Journal of Computing in Teacher Education*, 24, 38, 64.
- Valtonen, T., Sointu, E., Kukkonen, J., Kontkanen, S., Lambert, M. C., & Mäkitalo-Siegl, K. (2017). TPACK updated to measure pre-service teachers' twenty-first century skills. *Australasian Journal of Educational Technology*, 33(3).
- Wang, Y. (2019). Tech better, teach better: a TPACK model unit designed to implement communication competency inside Chinese language classes offered through American universities.

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